

**2020 Smathers Libraries Strategic Opportunities Grant
APPLICATION COVER SHEET
Application due: May 15, 2020, 5:00PM**

Principal Investigator (PI) Name: John D. Metz, Ph.D.

X Check here if this is your first grant application where you will serve as a principal investigator (PI).

Department: Information Sciences Email: jmetz3@vols.utk.edu Phone: 123-456-7890

Additional project applicants, please give name, email, and brief role for each:

- William A. Link, Ph.D., University of Florida, Department of History – Co-PI
- Chris Davidson, Georgia State Archivist – State records liaison

Title of grant project For Kin and Creditor: The Middle Georgia Historic Probate Data Project

Project abstract (no more than 100 words):

This project draws on a sample of 228 probate records from the Georgia counties of Crawford, Franklin, and Jasper between 1880-1910. These records provide an alternative approach to measuring wealth over time. The abundance of data from these three rural counties makes it possible to link probate inventories showing the composition of household assets at the time of death with sales, tax, and census data to reveal specific trends in household assets over time. The goal is to offer this dataset online for free so that others can explore the transition from traditional production and exchange systems to market capitalism.

Funds requested (Limit of **\$5,000**): \$5,000.00

Describe how the 10% mandatory cost share will be met (be specific):

The Georgia State Archives will provide the mandatory cost share of 10% of \$5,000 or \$500 to be applied to the digitization of the original state and local records from which indexes were made. These high resolution, archival-quality surrogates will be linked to the indexes and offered at no cost online to promote accessibility and use of the data set. The University of Florida Department of Research Program Development will also provide subvention to cover the salary of William A. Link for the duration of the project. Letters from the Georgia State Archives and the Department of Research Program Development are attached to this proposal.

Please list the library resources/departments needed for this project and the name of the person authorizing the intended use and date authorized. Each authorizing person must initial their approval and confirmation of the availability of resources for this project. If you need more room, continue on a separate page.

Departmental Resources Required for Project as applicable including cost share contributions	Chair or Authorizing Individual	Approving Initials	Date Authorized
Project Investigator, Data coordinator	John D. Metz, Ph.D.	JDM	April 23, 2020
Co-Principal Investigator	William A. Link, Ph.D.	WAL	April 23, 2020
Georgia State Archives Liaison	Christopher M. Davidson, J.D.	CD	April 23, 2020

I confirm receipt of approvals from all project team members to participate in this project as described in the narrative and budget:

John D. Metz, Ph.D.
PI Signature

April 23, 2020
Date

I support this project and approve the assignment of the described duties to the PI.

Herman Q. McGillicuddy, Ph.D.
Dept. Chair Signature

April 23, 2020
Date

2020 Smathers Libraries Strategic Opportunities Grant
PROJECT PROPOSAL NARRATIVE and BUDGET NARRATIVE
Application due: May 15, 2020, 5:00PM

FOR KIN AND CREDITOR: THE MIDDLE GEORGIA HISTORIC PROBATE DATA PROJECT

PROPOSAL NARRATIVE

Length: Maximum 4 pages of text (single-space)

a) Describe the project: goals, objectives, activities, etc.

This project draws on a sample of 228 probate records from the Georgia counties of Crawford, Franklin, and Jasper between 1880 and 1910. These records provide an alternative approach to measuring wealth over time. The abundance of data from these three rural counties makes it possible to link probate inventories showing the composition of household assets at the time of death with sales, tax, and census data to reveal specific trends in household assets over time. The goal is to offer this dataset online for free so that others can explore the transition from traditional production and exchange systems to market capitalism.

The Middle Georgia Historic Probate Data Project will serve as a pilot for how finer-grained economic data might be made available to a wide range of users, from economists and historians to local researchers and genealogists. While there are many sources and outlets for big data in the social realm at the federal and state levels, data at the local level is nearly non-existent online because it is so labor-intensive to collect.

Dr. John Metz (PI) will oversee every aspect of the project. He will coordinate with Christopher Davidson of the Georgia State Archives to develop workflows for sending microfilm from the archives and Georgia localities to be digitized by Backstage Library Works (BSLW) at their reformatting/preservation facility in Bethlehem, Pennsylvania. Metz and Davidson will also work with BSLW to determine the technical specifications, file naming conventions, and digital quality review to be used. Metz and Davidson will also work closely to manage ingest into the digital asset management and preservation system (Rosetta) at the Georgia State Archives.

The project will be completed within 12 months. Once workflows and a web portal are developed in conjunction with the Georgia State Archives in the first two months, the project team will digitize approximately 2,000 images of state and local records used to create the 36 indexes (12 for each county) aggregated by the number of acres owned by the decedent (e.g. 50-99 acres, 100-149 acres). Digitization will be completed using existing microfilm, numbering approximately 75 reels. Metz and Link will begin cataloging as digitized images are returned from the reformatting vendor. While this will primarily involve retrospective cataloging to enhance existing records, a small percentage of original cataloging is expected (e.g. loan documents and other financial papers mixed in with the other documentation needed to settle an estate). A comprehensive finding aid will be created once the collection is catalogued. The project team will begin working with curriculum developers from Georgia Department of Education as the cataloging winds down to develop lesson plans to teach students about using alternative historical resources like census, tax, and probate records. The team will also begin promoting the resource through the state archives and department of education websites, as well as through social media as the new web portal is unveiled.

The objectives include the following:

- The creation of a new, freely accessible online resource featuring 2,000 digitized images linked to 36 highly detailed indexes;
- New finding aids and MARC records for the digitized documents;
- Workflows for creating, curating, and preserving historical data;
- And, a model of best practices and guidance documentation for cultural heritage institutions that will allow them to participate in The Middle Georgia Historical Data Project or to develop their own repository.

- b) State why this project is important (e.g., what need does it address, what will it accomplish, who benefits, how does it support the [mission and strategic directions](#) of the library).

The Middle Georgia Historic Probate Data Project fills the need for fine-grained economic and historic data and meets the needs of users ranging from academic researchers to local historians and genealogists. It provides access to data that is rarely accessible outside of a paywall (e.g. Ancestry.com). The project will serve as a pilot for academics and other researchers who do quantitative analysis to put their raw data to use after they have completed their studies. It supports the strategic goal of the University of Florida Smathers Libraries of “Digital and Digitized Collections” by offering high-quality digitized images linked to detailed indexes to the public for free. The project is also an excellent example of a “Transformative Collaboration” between university researchers, government archivists, and localities by creating value-added resources that will appeal to many.

- c) What are the innovative components of this project?

The innovative aspects of this project are in the nature of the data used, the multi-institutional partnership, and the model for presenting fine-grained historical and economic data. Household-level data is hard to extract since it is labor-intensive and typically done individually or in small groups. Moreover, these data tend not to be shared once the initial research project is complete. While partnerships on collaboration are typical in an academic setting, it is less so when it comes to state and (particularly) local government. In this situation, academics see that their research is preserved and shared, the state archives provides greater accessibility, and understaffed local records repositories see that the collections in their care can be made available with little effort. Finally, this project is scalable to meet the needs and interests of the users. Hopefully, historians will see this as a way for their hard-won data is preserved and used into the future.

- d) Compare and contrast the proposed project to other similar projects in academic libraries.

Projects of this type are rare in an academic setting due to the way in which researchers working in history have traditionally conducted their work, guarding hard-gathered data and keeping it throughout their career to feed on-going research interests. Perhaps the closest example is the Integrated Public Use Microdata Series (IPUMS) database. Twenty-five years in the making, this repository of freely accessible population data is the result of a partnership between federal agencies, genealogical organizations, and even other nations (IPUMS-International). This top-down, big data has proven its worth in the level of use it sees and the number of projects it has inspired. The Middle Georgia project proposed here intends to offer a model for how grass-roots big data might be offered to offer a fuller spectrum of possibilities. The only other historical data

and digitization projects tend to be niche, thematic, or period specific, like private papers collections, “Voyages: The Trans-Atlantic Slave Trade Database” (Emory), “Virginia Untold: The African American Narrative” (Library of Virginia), and “Freedom on the Move” (Cornell).

- e) Explicitly describe the resources needed and committed to complete the project and impacts on other departments (e.g., personnel, equipment, supplies, travel, space, training, IT support, preservation, cataloging, other).

Given that the data has already been collected as part of another project (Metz dissertation), the proposed project has limited resource needs. Moreover, partnering with the Georgia State Archives involves a partner that can bring significant capabilities and resources to bear. Digitization will be completed by a well-established outside vendor with whom we have worked in the past, Metz and link will organize the project and catalogue the materials, and the Georgia State Archives will provide an in-house web developer to the project, as well as coordinate the curriculum development with their sister agency, the Georgia Department of Education. The state archives will also spearhead the promotion of the new web portal.

- f) Provide a plan of action for the project. Include a timeline to show that the project can be completed in 12 months, and specify activities and roles to be performed by the principal investigator (PI) and others involved in the project.

The Middle Georgia Historic Probate Data Project												
Activities	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun
Develop Workflows												
Build Web Portal												
Digitization												
Cataloging												
Develop Educational Curriculum												
Unveil Portal												
Promote Portal												

- g) If the project is collection specific: Who owns the collection and where is it located? What copyright issues, if any, is the applicant anticipating?

All of the materials used in this project are federal, state, or local records that are in the public domain with no copyright or use restrictions. The decennial census returns from 1790 to 1940 providing county-level data are freely available online through the United States Census Bureau

(<https://www.census.gov/prod/www/decennial.html>). The Georgia State Archives in Morrow, Georgia, is the official repository for all Georgia state documents, including tax records and agricultural censuses. While the state archives has administrative oversight of the records in localities across the state, the records fall under the direct jurisdiction of the local courts or their designee (e.g. historical society, library, state archives). The Georgia State Archives has microfilmed many of these records. All indexed data were compiled by Link and Metz and are offered for use under a Creative Commons-Attribution-Non-Commercial-Share Alike (CC BY-NC-SA) license.

- h) Provide a means of measuring the success of the project. What are the expected results, final product, and projected use?

Success will be measured in the level of use the repository sees once it is unveiled. The broad range of users expected include economic, historical, and social researchers in academia as well as avocational historians and genealogists. This use can easily be tracked and assessed to determine which additional resources will enhance the value of the resource. Success will also attract other researchers with large bodies of value-added data to contribute.

- i) How will the project team disseminate information about the project, and how will it share results?

The Georgia State Archives will create a web portal to this collection and take responsibility for promoting its use via its website and through its established contacts in the historical, genealogical and educational communities. Moreover, the state archives will work with the Georgia Department of Education to develop curriculum ties to the Middle Georgia Project and lesson plans that make use of the data. Full credit will be given to Dr. Link, Dr. Metz, and the Smathers Libraries for developing the resource.

- j) What are the long-term financial implications if the project is successful? For example, if a pilot project using e-book readers is successful, what would be the cost to the Libraries, annually, to support a new loaned e-book reader service?

As mentioned previously, success is measured primarily in the level of use the database enjoys. Heavy use among researchers and academics makes the resource attractive for grants to expand it. IPUMS, for example, has attracted more than 140 million in grant funds over the past quarter century. Heavy use among the educational community could mean increased funding from the Georgia Department of Education. Ultimately, use of any type meets the goals of the Georgia State Archives to provide access to unique historical documentation.

- k) Provide a plan for what will happen to equipment/supplies purchased with these funds after the project ends.

There will be no equipment purchased using these funds. Grant support from the Smathers Libraries will be used to pay for salaries (in part) for project staff, travel, and digitization services provided by Backstage Library Works.

BUDGET NARRATIVE

Length: Maximum 1 page of text (single-space)

- l) Provide a detailed explanation for how each expense was calculated.

Salaries were calculated using the annual salaries for John Metz and William Link at the university of Florida. The effort for both was calculated at 5%. The University of Florida Department of Research Program Development will also provide subvention to cover the salary of William Link for the duration of the project and will serve as a cost share. Travel costs for the two-night trip to Georgia for consultation at the beginning of the project were calculated using the federal General Services Administration (GSA) Travel Guidelines for allowable expenditures (<https://www.gsa.gov/travel/plan-book/per-diem-rates>). Postage was calculated using the USPS.com postage calculators, which includes both packaging and shipping costs. Finally, the estimate for BSLW to digitize 2,000 microfilm images to create uncompressed 1500 ppi 48-bit RGB Tiffs was provided in a formal estimated in the amount of \$3,000.

- m) Provide a justification for each expense required to carry out the project.

The cost of two individuals working at 5% of their annual salary represents the minimum effort required to accomplish this project in a year. The trip to Georgia at the beginning of the project for both of these individuals is necessary to meet with the archives and digitization teams, as well as to select the microfilm to be used. Shipping the microfilm to BSLW in Pennsylvania is the cheapest option, and using a vendor to digitize the images and perform all of the necessary quality control will ultimately save time and money.

- n) Provide a detailed explanation of the PI's role vis-à-vis effort (does not qualify as a cost share match).

John Metz (PI) will spend an estimated 5% effort to oversee the project, while William Link's time will be underwritten by a university research grant.

- o) Provide a detailed explanation of the contributed cost share by project team members toward the required 10 % matching requirement.

The Georgia State Archives will provide the mandatory cost share of 10% of \$5,000 or \$500 to be applied to the digitization of the original state and local records from which indexes were made. Additional cost share will be provided in terms of the portion of Dr. Metz's (\$1,500) and Dr. Link's (\$3,750) salaries that will not be paid by the Smathers Libraries grant funds.

NOTE: Please see application guidelines for additional instructions to support budget narrative content.

Strategic Opportunities Grant Budget Form 2020-2021

Please add lines to table as needed. If you need help completing this form, please contact Bess de Farber, PH# 273-2519.

1. Salaries and Fringe

Name of Person	% of effort	Grant Funds	Cost Share	Total
Metz	5	\$2,000.00	\$1,500.00	\$3,500.00
Link	5	\$0.00	\$3,750.00	\$3,750.00
SUBTOTAL		\$2,000.00	\$5,250.00	\$7,250.00

2. Equipment

Item	Quantity times Cost	Grant Funds	Cost Share	Total
		\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00
SUBTOTAL		\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00

3. Supplies

Item	Quantity times Cost	Grant Funds	Cost Share	Total
		\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00
SUBTOTAL		\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00

4. Travel

From/To	# of people/# of days	Grant Funds	Cost Share	Total
Travel - FL to GA - consultation	2 people for 2 nights/ 1 car	\$350.00	\$0.00	\$350.00
SUBTOTAL		\$350.00	\$0.00	\$350.00

5. Other (Vendor costs, etc. Provide detail in Budget Narrative section.)

Item	Quantity times cost	Grant Funds	Cost Share	Total
Backstage Library Works	\$1.50 per image – scan & QC	\$2,500.00	\$500.00	\$3,000.00
Postage	4 boxes @ \$37.50 ea.	\$150.00	\$0.00	\$150.00
SUBTOTAL		\$2,650.00	\$500.00	\$3,150.00

Total Direct Costs (add subtotals of items 1-5)	Grant Funds	Cost Share	Total
	\$5,000.00	\$5,750.00	\$10,750.00

Middle Georgia Historic Probate Data Project

A Data Management Plan created using DMPTool

Creators: John Metz

Affiliation: Non-Partner Institution

ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6631-9810

Template: Digital Curation Centre (DCC)

Project abstract:

This project draws on a sample of 228 probate records from the Georgia counties of Crawford, Franklin, and Jasper between 1880 and 1910. These records provide an alternative approach to measuring wealth over time. The probate inventories showing the composition of household assets at the time of death are linked with sales, tax, and census data to reveal specific trends in household assets over time. The goal is to offer this dataset online for free so that others can explore the transition from traditional production and exchange systems to market capitalism.

Data Collection:

The following data types will be created as part of the project:

- 36 indexes (12 for each county) aggregated by the size of land holding and detailing 82 separate variables, saved as CSV files.
- A ReadMe file to explain the creation, composition, and use of the indexes.
- Nearly 2,000 uncompressed 1500 ppi 48-bit RGB Tiffs of probate, census, and tax records.
- Project documentation and transcriptions saved as PDF and text files.

Documentation and Metadata:

The Middle Georgia Data Project documentation will include the following metadata:

- File name - e.g. FRA-0001.jpg or FRA-050-099.csv
- File Format - e.g. PDF, CSV, TIFF
- Variables: variable, name, variable label, value label name
- Creator - e.g. Metz, John D.
- Software used to create file - e.g. Word 2016, Excel 2016
- Operating system in which file was made - e.g. MAC OSX Catalina
- Date of file creation - e.g. 2020-01-24
- Date of last file modification - e.g. 2020-01-25
- Processing history of file - chronology of changes made to file including the name of any contributors.

Ethics and Legal Compliance:

All of the records used for this the project are in the public domain and have no known privacy or restriction issues.

All data related to the Middle Georgia Historic Probate Data Project is made available under Creative Commons License [CC: BY-NC-SA](#).

Storage and Backup:

All data will be kept on servers at the Georgia State Archives, which will be backed up weekly throughout the course of the project and beyond. During the project, data will be collected and processed by the project team consisting of John Metz, William Link, Christopher Davidson, and other state archives staff. At 2TB of storage, there is no concern that the data generated will exceed the archive's storage capacity. All remote work completed on project files will be done using a secure VPN connection. Access to the digital project files will be restricted until the launch of the public portal at the end of the project. State Archivist Christopher Davidson serves as the chief security officer for the state archives.

Selection and Preservation:

All of the data and files generated as part of the project will be turned over to the Georgia State Archives for long-term preservation. The State Archives is the primary repository responsible for maintaining Georgia's archival heritage, and they have the staff and expertise necessary to ensure the long-term preservation and access of these data. These files will be considered permanent and stored in perpetuity.

Upon completion of the project, the files will be shared via the Georgia State Archives website under their "Research" section. Accompanying metadata will be available for download with the data files. These holdings will be offered under a Creative Commons License [CC: BY-NC-SA](#), whereby users may use, adapt, and share the data in any way, but they must acknowledge John Metz, William Link, and the Georgia State Archives if these data are shared or transformed. Use of the data can only be noncommercial and any creations made using the data must be shared according to the same Creative Commons terms of the BY-NC-SA License. Moreover, no additional restrictions may be placed on the shared data or any derivatives created from the original data.

Responsibilities and Resources:

John Metz will be the primary contact throughout the project and will direct inquiries as appropriate. He will also be primarily responsible for data management during the project, while the Georgia State Archives will manage data backups on a weekly basis. Once the project is complete, the Georgia State Archives will assume complete oversight and ownership of the data.